

Experimental Evaluation of Detection Speed in Optical Based Internal Arc Fault Control Devices Using Flashlight-Simulated Arc Illuminance

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Abstract—Optical based Internal Arc Fault Control Devices (IACDs) play a crucial role in the detection speed of arc faults in low-voltage switchgear assemblies. They can utilize different types of sensors (point and line) and contain different types of output (semiconductor and relay). The configuration of an IACD will influence the total detection time of such a system. This article presents a comparison of the detection speed of commercially available optical based IACDs. It describes the method used to measure the speed of operation of IACDs using a flashlight that simulates the illuminance of an electrical arc. The results are presented and compared using box plots and Individual Moving Range (I-MR) charts. Box plots offer at glance comparison of influence of different test conditions on the speed of operation, and I-MR charts help to evaluate the measurement method. The measurements also indicate a dependence of the reaction times of the tested IACD on the energy of the flashlight. This information is useful in designing the proper placement of optical sensors and allows the selection of a system configuration that will ensure the fastest reaction time under given test conditions applicable to low-voltage switchgear assemblies.

Index Terms—Active arc protection, arc detection, arc fault, arcing classes, IEC arc standards, low-voltage switchgear, optical sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internal arc faults in low-voltage switchgear assemblies, although rare, cause sudden changes in temperature and pressure resulting from the flow of an electrical current through the air. The mentioned phenomena have the potential to destroy an assembly and can be dangerous to personnel in the vicinity of the assembly during an internal arc fault. The causes of internal arc faults can be divided into direct ones (human error, leaving of a tool, entry of rodents) and those of long-term nature, possible to be detected (for eg. detection of loose connections through monitoring of their temperatures) [1]. The introduction of Internal Arc Fault Mitigation Systems (IAMS) that allow quick detection of such a fault and its conversion to a fault of different nature, such as a bolted fault, results in enhanced protection of personnel and assembly. Reduction of the duration of an internal arc fault leads to the limitation of the electrical energy released during the fault, thus ensuring the reduction of the effects of internal arc fault [2] resulting from both human errors and long term causes.

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Over the years, many solutions have been developed that limit the energy of an internal arc fault. Those have been presented in [3], [4] and include Zone Selective Interlocking, Reduced Energy Let Through, and the use of fast current limiting fuses. However, the quickest way to detect an internal arc fault, which leads to the reduction of its energy, is the deployment of optical based detection sensors, which are a part of Internal Arc Fault Control Device (IACD).

In its simplest form, IAMS will consist of optical based IACD, which cooperates with a circuit breaker installed in an incoming circuit of an assembly. In that application, the circuit breaker functions as an Internal Arc Fault Reduction Device (IARD). After detection of an internal arc fault by a sensor that reacts to light emitted by an arc, an IACD sends a signal to trip the breaker. Cutting off the power by the circuit breaker causes an arc to extinguish. The speed of operation of IACD is of key importance in limiting the effects of an arc fault.

In the available literature, articles can be found that describe the development and design of optical arc detection sensors [5], [6]. Those concentrate on a spectrum of the radiation generated by an arc and its transformation to visible light that can be detected by photo-elements. Another possible solution is the detection of ultraviolet (UV) or infrared (IR) radiation [7], [8]. However, the authors of this article are not aware of any commercially available IACDs based on sensors that react to UV or IR radiation. Yet another possibility in the area of arc detection sensors is the use of photovoltaic panels to detect the light emitted by an arc [9]. The first tests of such solution show successful arc detection starting at relatively low current values of 2.1 kA. However, it is still necessary to check their reaction to undesired detection of switching arcs generated by devices installed in low-voltage switchgear assemblies.

In the case of optical based IACDs, it is possible to use point sensors, based on a photo element or optical fiber covered along its length, and for some of the IACDs it is also possible to use line sensors based on uncovered optical fiber, which can react to an optical signal along its length. An example of an IACD that works with the two types of sensors (point and line) is presented in [10].

Detection of an arc fault is also possible without optical detection but based on measurement of current and voltage in a circuit as presented in [11]. The measured current and voltage waveforms are analyzed in the time domain to detect

the characteristic points: the step change of the voltage as a result of the arc ignition and the temporary decrease of the current value. The mentioned decrease of current value is better observed on the waveform of current derivative over time and thus it is much easier to detect that change. However, solutions based on the analysis of measured current and voltage waveforms are not commonly used for parallel arc detection. This type of arc fault appears when the arc burns between live parts or between live parts and grounded parts of a switchgear assembly. Parallel arcs are a type of fault in a low-voltage switchgear assembly that results in dangerous consequences for both personnel and the switchgear itself. On the other hand, the method of arc fault detection based on measurement of current and voltage waveforms is successfully deployed in devices called Arc Fault Detection Devices (AFDDs), which are used to detect a series arc. Series arcs are observed, e.g., in domestic electrical installations on the terminals of the devices or when a line conductor continuity is impaired. An evolution of the idea of detecting an arc based on the measurement of current and voltage is the use of spectral analysis of those to signals in various faults [12], [13], [14] or the use of a dedicated artificial neural network to classify series arcs in domestic electrical installations [15].

One of the challenges in using the optical based detection devices is making sure that such device would not operate when exposed to external light sources and the switching arcs caused by devices installed in a switchgear assembly during their normal operation. The IACD equipped with current measurement protects the system from being triggered by an external light source [3], [16]. When it comes to the detection of switching arcs caused by the devices working in an assembly, the system can be protected from them by proper placement of the sensors [10] or by detection of an additional signal. One of the possibilities is the detection of an overpressure generated by an arc. But it is rather difficult and can lead to some delays in arc detection [17] and consequently influence the amount of energy released in an arc fault, which should be as low as possible. It is worth mentioning that in the case of low-voltage switchgear assemblies, a proper design of such a sensor is necessary that overpressure detection occurs before the pressure relief flaps installed in the assembly are opened. Based on [18], the detection of overpressure by a dedicated sensor should take into account overpressure values as low as 7 kPa. Instead of detection of pressure change during an arc fault, it is possible to detect acoustic pressure. The optical and acoustic signals form a pair detection of which enables one to identify an arc fault [17]. This solution does not require measurement of current values, which means that no current transformers or Rogowski coils are needed. The design and description of a sensor that detects both signals is presented in [6] and [17].

The way in which the detection signal is sent to IACD is also important. It can be sent using an optical fiber or a copper wire. In an optical fiber, the signal is attenuated more than in a copper conductor. For that reason, sensors with a connection using optical fiber have lengths measured in tenths of meters, whereas copper wires allow lengths of hundreds of meters [19]. However, an advantage of using an optical

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF FUNCTIONALITIES OF TESTED IACDS

Functionality	System A	System B	System C
Cooperation with an optical point sensor	YES	YES	YES
Cooperation with an optical line sensor	YES	YES	NO
Verification of the correct connection of sensors to the control unit	YES	YES	YES
High-speed semiconductor output	YES	YES	NO
Relay output	YES	YES	YES

fiber is immunity to electromagnetic disturbance compared to a copper wire. To address that disadvantage of copper wires, when they are used to send a signal to a control device of IACD, it is necessary to use shielded copper wires.

This article presents a comparison of the detection speed of commercially available optical based internal arc fault detection devices. Those units can have different types of outputs (semiconductor based, also named as high-speed outputs, and relay based) and can cooperate with different types of optical sensors (point and/or line). The devices analyzed in this article are marked as System A, System B, and System C, and their functionality is compared in Table I.

Some comparison of the detection speed of optical based internal arc fault detection devices can be found in [11]. However, it is more focused on the comparison of the speed of the algorithm detecting an internal arc fault based on the measurement of current and voltage waveforms with the speed of optical detection. This article presents a more detailed comparison of IACDs, focusing on different types of optical sensors (point and line) and different types of output (semiconductor and relay). Additionally, the presented study includes two types of point sensors: one designed using optical fiber connected to an IACD and the other using copper wire for connection to an IACD. The advantage of the speed of operation of the semiconductor output in limiting the effects of internal arc faults was already described in [3]. It must be observed that there are IACDs available that provide only relay type of outputs, which was reproduced in this article by tests of System C.

This paper describes the method used to measure the speed of operation of Systems A, B, and C using a flashlight that simulates the illuminance of an electrical arc. This method was compared with the illuminance values measured during an arc fault presented in [20]. The reaction times of the tested IACDs were measured with a Yokogawa DL750 oscilloscope. Box plots were used to analyze and compare the measurements of the reaction times of IACDs. This type of plot can be used to present the measurement points without the requirement of assuming a statistical distribution and enables easy comparison of median and ranges of measured data under varying measurement conditions. To evaluate the measurement method, the authors used a statistical control chart called I-MR, which presents the individual measurement points (hence letter I) and the moving range (MR) of the measurements. I-MR charts allow one to check if the measurement points

Fig. 1. Station for measurements of the detection speed of IACDs.

contain only a common cause variation, which is desired, and no special cause variation. The method used in this paper using a flashlight and statistical analysis of recorded measurement data has not been described in the reviewed literature.

Based on the measurements, it was also possible to develop a dependence of the reaction times of the tested IACDs on the energy of the flashlight, which provides insightful data for the body of knowledge regarding internal arc fault mitigation systems (IAMS). This variation of the measurement conditions was intended to simulate the influence of different distances of a sensor from the location of the burning arc. The conducted measurements are a valuable source of an IACD configuration that provides the quickest reaction after the detection of an internal arc. This approach serves as a screening method to select the most promising IACD setup to be used in the internal arc fault test. The internal arc fault test is a destructive test associated with the significant cost and necessity of using a dedicated high-power laboratory. The method described in the paper allows to limit the cost related to the testing of IAMS in internal arc fault test conditions by selecting the setups with the shortest reaction time. The results will also allow for the proper placement of sensors in a low-voltage

switchgear assembly and the selection of the type of sensor that is going to be the least sensitive to the detection of switching arcs caused by proper operation of devices installed in an assembly. An additional motivation to carry out the measurements in this article is the imminent publication of the technical specification IEC TS 61641 [21], which introduces the new arcing classes that are possible to assign to defined zones in an assembly only when an IAMS is installed.

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to check the detection speed of the selected three, commercially available optical based IACDs, a dedicated measurement station was built. In that test station, a source of light that simulates an internal arc was a regulated energy flashlight. Table II presents the selected properties of the flashlight in the product datasheet [22].

The lamp was placed at the defined distance to the optical sensors used to detect the optical effects related to the electric arc. It was important to make sure that all three IACDs were triggered at the same time. Therefore, the optical sensors of all three IACDs, marked as A, B, and C, were placed on the same plane. This action enabled a comparison of the activation of

TABLE II
SELECTED PROPERTIES OF THE FLASHLIGHT USED TO TRIGGER IACDS
[22]

Model	Pulse 1200
Maximum energy	1200 W·s
Control of the lamp energy	1/32–1/1 (37.5 W·s–1200 W·s [31 regulation steps of the lamp energy])
Light temperature	5600 ± 200 K
Guide number (mISO 100, max. energy, reflective lamp shade)	110
Duration of the flash	1/800 s @ 1/1; 1/2000 s @ 1/32

all IACDs under the same illumination conditions generated by the flashlight and allowed for consideration of the varying conditions that may be generated by the flashlight. The scheme of the station used for the measurements of reaction times is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2. Flashlight used as a light source to simulate optical effects of an arc fault: (a) lamp with a lamp shade without reflective material, used for point sensors test; (b) lamp with a lamp shade with reflective material used for line sensors test.

The way this station was designed is based on the IACDs testing guidelines shown in IEC 60947-9-2 [23]. However, the source of light used in this paper is different. Instead of a tungsten-halogen lamp, a flashlight was used. In the method described in the IEC standard, the light source used (tungsten-halogen lamp) is intended to simulate the influence of ambient light in a room where low-voltage switchgear can be installed. IACDs are checked for immunity of optical detection systems to such ambient light conditions assuring prevention of nuisance operation of the system. In the measurements conducted and presented in the article the goal was to use a light source

that simulates an arc fault, to find a set of parameters (distance to the sensors and flashlight energy) that can trigger all IACDs and to show that changing flashlight energy can also have an impact on the reaction times of IACDs. All of that serves as a screening method to select the fastest operating IACD setup. The limitation of this method is the fact that a flash lamp generates a high illuminance but for a very short period of time.

The flashlight used in the measurements has two types of lamp shade shown in Fig. 2. For the test of the optical point sensor, a lamp shade without reflective material was used (see Fig. 2(a)).

The test program for IACDs with point sensors included three scenarios:

- 1) Fixed distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 113 cm, maximum flashlight energy, 15 measurements.
- 2) Fixed distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 70 cm (to check the reaction time based on the change of distance to a light source), maximum flashlight energy, 5 measurements.
- 3) Fixed distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 70 cm, change of flashlight energy from maximum to minimum value that was still detected by the sensors.

It must be emphasized that the distances of the flashlight from the sensors were arbitrarily selected in order to check the influence of the distance of the flashlight on the reaction times of the IACDs and to ensure detection by IACDs in the widest range of flashlight energy for all types of IACDs. The number of repetitions was selected to provide a meaningful set of data that can be plotted using box plots to indicate the range of the reaction times of IACDs.

Based on the flashlight datasheet and using (1) for the value of illuminance E based on [24] and [25], it was possible to calculate the value of illuminance for the distances of the light source used in the measurements (see Table III). It should be observed that the illuminance formula contains a guide number (GN), which is linked to a lamp shade, as well as the energy setting of the flashlight. The GN value given in the datasheet is at maximum energy value and with a lamp shade with reflective material, and this is how the values in Table III were calculated.

$$E = \frac{CGN^2}{r^2 t_f S}, \quad (1)$$

where

- E illuminance (lx);
- GN Guide Number equal to 110 based on flashlight datasheet at maximum flashlight energy and with a lamp shade with reflective material;
- C calibration constant for incident light meters equal to 250 (based on [24] for illuminance of flat surfaces);
- r distance from the light source (m);
- S ISO sensitivity equal to 100 based on flashlight datasheet;
- t_f flash duration equal to 1/800 s for maximum power of flashlight based on the datasheet (s).

The illuminance values shown in Table III do not simulate the internal arc fault conditions due to the way a flash is

Fig. 3. Station for measurements of the detection speed of System A with a line sensor. Light sources include two cases: with a lamp shade with reflective material and without reflective material (shown in upper left hand corner as an alternative light source setup).

generated. However, the illumination values can be compared with the published values recorded for an arc fault. Based on [20] illuminance measured at a distance of 3 m from the ignition point of the arc in a three phase arc fault on the busbars at 2.7 kV and the prospective fault current of 32 kA was equal to $13.1 \cdot 10^6$ lx. The flashlight used with the assumed value of the calibration constant C based on [24] generates a lower value of illuminance than the value obtained in [20] recalculated to the distances of the flashlight from the sensors that were used in the measurements. However, it must be observed that the arc voltage values in the case of low-voltage switchgear assemblies will be lower than the values presented in [20] due to the smaller clearances applicable to low-voltage assemblies. Additionally, the duration of flash generated by the flashlight is much shorter than the optical effects during an arc fault. Taking into account the conditions discussed above, the illuminance values presented in Table III, valid for a flashlight with a reflective material lamp shade, serve as estimated values for comparison purposes. These are the limitations of the method used. Nevertheless, it was possible to trigger all three IACDs. Therefore, the values of illuminance obtained with the flashlight are sufficient to verify the behavior of the three optical based arc detection devices.

As a second step, System A with a line sensor was tested.

TABLE III
VALUES OF ILLUMINANCE GENERATED BY THE FLASHLIGHT WITH A LAMP SHADE WITH REFLECTIVE MATERIAL AT MAXIMUM ENERGY

Distance r (m)	Illuminance E at 1/800 s (10^6 lx)
0.7	49.4
0.91	29.2
1.13	18.95

The measurement station is shown in Fig. 3. The line sensor used for testing is characterized by a lower sensitivity to an external flash. In the case of installation of the lamp shade without reflective material (Fig. 2(a)), it was mandatory to place the flashlight very close to the sensor. According to the first point of the test program below, it was as close as 5 cm. The larger distances of the flashlight from the sensor resulted in the lack of detection of the flash by the sensor. For that reason, measurements were performed with the second type of lamp shade (Fig. 2(b)). The test program was the following:

- 1) flashlight with lamp shade without reflective material, fixed distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 5 cm, maximum flashlight energy, 15 measurements.
- 2) flashlight with lamp shade with reflective material, fixed

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Measurement of the reaction time of the IACD outputs: (a) view on all signals measured for point sensors; (b) close up on the area showing contact bouncing of the relay output of System C (cursor marks the place up to which a measurement is made).

distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 70 cm, maximum flashlight energy, 15 measurements.

- flashlight with lamp shade with reflective material, fixed distance of the flashlight from the sensors: 70 cm, change of the flashlight energy from maximum to minimum value that was still detected by the sensors.

In the case of the test of two types of optical sensors (point and line), to measure the reaction time of outputs of tested IACDs, an oscilloscope was used. The sampling frequency of the oscilloscope is equal to 10 MS/s for the type of input modules used for the measurements [26]. Every output of the tested IACDs connected a positive line conductor of an external 24 V DC power supply. That power supply unit was used to detect the moment in which an IACD output was activated. Activation of this output was recorded as a step increase in the voltage from 0 V (open output) to 24 V (activated output). The triggering signal was the edge of a signal that activates the flashlight, which was also a voltage signal. The measurement of the reaction time of a given IACD

Fig. 5. Box plot with its characteristic values. IQR - Inter-Quartile Range.

was based on measuring the distance between the cursors in a software provided by the manufacturer of the oscilloscope. In the case of relay based outputs, which are characterized by contact bouncing, the vertical cursor was placed in the area of the measurement where contact bouncing was not observed. The idea of the measurement is shown in Fig. 4.

The yellow signal in Fig.4 shows the moment of trigger of the flashlight. The edge of this signal triggered the measurement with an oscilloscope. The remaining colors in Fig.4 mark the following signals: for System A, red, activation of the semiconductor output, orange, activation of the relay output; for System B, violet, activation of the semiconductor output, green, activation of the relay output; for System C, blue, activation of the relay output. System C was not equipped with a semiconductor output.

III. RESULTS OF MEASUREMENTS

As a result of the measurements conducted, reaction times of three IACD systems were obtained from the moment the flashlight was activated to the activation of an output of a particular IACD. The measurements in the described conditions were repeated to verify the range of the reaction times. To present the measured times, box plots were used. Fig. 5 presents a box plot with marking of its characteristic values.

This type of plot presents, in a clear way, the minimum and maximum values, as well as the median value of the measured reaction times. Additionally, it allows us to compare the results obtained for the same IACD but in different measurement conditions (i.e. distance of the flashlight to a sensor or at fixed distance of the flashlight to a sensor, but with changing values of the flashlight energy). The box plots were plotted using Matplotlib Python package.

A. Reaction times of IACDs with point sensors

Fig. 6 presents box plots of the reaction times of all 3 IACD systems in a test where the light source (a flashlight) was

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6. Reaction times for: (a) System A - semiconductor output; (b) System B - semiconductor output; (c) relay outputs of all tested systems. Distance of the light source (the flashlight) from the sensors equal to 113 cm.

placed at a distance of 113 cm from the sensors. During that test, the flashlight energy was set to a maximum (1200 W·s).

The reactions times values of various types of IACDs outputs were also used to evaluate the influence of the measurement method used on the reaction times. For this purpose, I-MR control charts were used, which present the individual measurement points (I part of the control chart) and the difference between the two consecutive measurement points (MR part of the control chart). The \overline{MR} value visible on the control chart is calculated using (2). In general, control charts allow us to check if the measurement points contain only a common cause variation or if there is also a special cause variation present. Based on the Six Sigma methodology, several tests are used on the data in a control chart [27]. The simplest of those tests is observation of points outside the Upper Control Limit (UCL) (3) and the Lower Control limit (LCL) (4) marked with red horizontal lines in Fig. 7. Fig. 7 shows the I-MR control charts for the tested IACDs and their different types of output. The formulas used to create an I-MR chart are the following [27]:

$$\overline{MR} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=2}^N |x_i - x_{i-1}|, \quad (2)$$

where

\overline{MR} average moving range;

N number of measurement points;

x_i measurement point i ;

x_{i-1} measurement point $i-1$.

The control limits marked with a red horizontal line in part I of the control chart are calculated as follows [27]:

$$UCL = \bar{x} + D_2 \overline{MR}, \quad (3)$$

$$LCL = \bar{x} - D_2 \overline{MR}, \quad (4)$$

where

\bar{x} average value;

UCL upper control limit;

LCL lower control limit;

D_2 a constant value used to calculate control limits for individual measurement points, equal to 2.66.

For the moving range (MR) part of the control chart, the lower control limit is equal to 0 and the upper control limit UCL_{MR} is calculated as follows [27]:

$$UCL_{MR} = D_4 \overline{MR}, \quad (5)$$

where D_4 is a constant used to calculate the upper control limit in the case of individual measurement points, where the range is the difference between the two consecutive measurement points, equal to 3.27.

Equations (2)–(5) were used in a Python script to create I-MR control charts of the measured reaction times. The charts were plotted using the Matplotlib package.

Analyzing the control charts in Fig. 7 it can be observed that System B shows points outside of control limits that can indicate that there is a special cause variation in the measurement

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig. 7. I-MR control charts for: (a) semiconductor output of System A; (b) semiconductor output of System B; (c) relay output of System A; (d) relay output of System B; (e) relay output of System C.

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig. 8. Influence of the distance of the light source (the flashlight) on the reaction time of the semiconductor outputs of IACDs: (a) System A; (b) System B. Distance of the light source to the sensors is given after a colon.

data. However, it must be noted that the measured system was not a new one but had been used in arc fault testing, which could have influenced the obtained measured data.

As a next step, the measurements were repeated with a changed distance of the light source (the flashlight) to the sensors, which was 70 cm. The light energy was unchanged and equal to 1200 W·s. The aim of this portion of the measurements was to check the influence of the light intensity on the reaction times of IACDs. Fig. 8 presents the comparison of the reaction times of the semiconductor outputs of systems A and B for the two cases: light source distance at 113 cm and at 70 cm.

Fig. 9 presents the same comparison, but for relay type outputs for all three IACD systems tested.

Tables IV and V present the differences in the reaction times obtained depending on the distance of the light source from the sensors. The columns contain the median, minimum, and maximum values, as well as the range calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum values.

(c)

Fig. 9. Influence of the distance of the light source (the flashlight) on the reaction time of the relay outputs of IACDs: (a) System A; (b) System B; (c) System C. Distance of the light source to the sensors is given after a colon.

TABLE IV
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR SEMICONDUCTOR
OUTPUTS OF SYSTEM A AND SYSTEM B

System - output type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - semiconductor - 113 cm	2.118	2.045	2.160	0.115
System A - semiconductor - 70 cm	1.636	1.618	1.684	0.066
Percent change	22.8%	20.9%	22.0%	42.6%
System B - semiconductor - 113 cm	0.516	0.495	0.536	0.041
System B - semiconductor - 70 cm	0.434	0.430	0.446	0.016
Percent change	15.9%	13.1%	16.8%	61.0%

TABLE V
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR RELAY OUTPUTS OF
SYSTEM A, SYSTEM B, AND SYSTEM C

System - output type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - relay - 113 cm	7.008	6.780	7.482	0.702
System A - relay - 70 cm	6.872	6.480	7.022	0.542
Percent change	1.9%	4.4%	6.1%	22.8%
System B - relay - 113 cm	8.378	8.012	8.715	0.703
System B - relay - 70 cm	8.248	7.866	8.406	0.540
Percent change	1.6%	1.8%	3.5%	23.2%
System C - relay - 113 cm	4.624	4.410	5.014	0.604
System C - relay - 70 cm	4.568	4.390	4.714	0.324
Percent change	1.2%	0.5%	6.0%	46.4%

Analyzing the data presented in Tables IV and V, it can be seen that the increase in illuminance by moving the light source closer to the sensors causes a noticeable reduction in the reaction times of the semiconductor outputs. For the relay outputs, this influence is less noticeable.

B. Influence of the flashlight energy change on the reaction times

As the next step of the measurement program, the influence of the change in flashlight energy on the reaction times of the tested IACDs was checked. Fig. 8 shows the influence of the distance from the light source on the reaction time of the semiconductor output. By analogy, the change of the flashlight energy at a constant distance to the sensors equal to 70 cm is more noticeable for this type of output. Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 present the dependence of the reaction time of the semiconductor outputs on the value of the flashlight energy, together with a power fit trend line.

The change in flashlight energy at a constant distance from the source to the sensors equal to 70 cm allowed us to establish that System A did not detect the flash of the light source energy setting below 134 W·s. The other systems detected the flash up to a minimum energy setting equal to 37.5 W·s.

The reaction time of the relay outputs of all three tested IACDs is shown in Fig. 12. The influence of the flashlight energy on that type of output is smaller than in the case of

Fig. 10. Influence of the flashlight energy change on the recorded reaction time of a semiconductor output of the System A along with a trend line, power fit equation, and correlation coefficient R^2 .

Fig. 11. Influence of the flashlight energy change on the recorded reaction time of a semiconductor output of the System B along with a trend line, power fit equation, and correlation coefficient R^2 .

semiconductor output. For that reason, a linear function trend line was used.

Analyzing the slope coefficients of the trend lines shown in Fig. 12, one can observe that the relay output of Systems A and B shows some dependence on the energy of the light source. The most independent of the energy of the light source is the relay output of System C.

C. Reaction times of system A with a line sensor

The measurement of the reaction times with a line sensor was made using the same method as for the point sensors. Only System A was tested with the use of that type of sensor. System B also has the option of using a line sensor, but it was not available at the time of measurement. In order to perform measurements in the distance of the light source to the sensor that are comparable to the measurements done on point

Fig. 12. Influence of the flashlight energy change on the recorded reaction time of relay outputs of all three tested IACDs.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13. Reaction times of semiconductor output (a) and relay output (b) of System A with the line sensor. Distance of the light source to a sensor (given after a colon): 5 cm.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14. I-MR control charts for System A with the line sensor: (a) semiconductor output; (b) relay output.

sensors, it was necessary to use the flashlight with a different lamp shade than in the case of point sensor measurements. The lamp shade used in point sensor measurement triggered System A with a line sensor only if the distance to the sensor was 5 cm. The results of measurements performed with the same lamp shade as used for point sensors (lamp shade without reflective material), at maximum flashlight energy (1200 W·s) are shown in Fig. 13. Fig. 14 shows the I-MR control charts for these measurements.

Fig. 15 shows the reaction times of System A when the lamp shade was changed to a version with reflective material (see Fig. 2(b)) compared to the measurements made with the lamp shade without reflective material shown in Fig. 13. In the case of the use of the lamp shade with reflective material, the flashlight was placed 70 cm from the sensor. The energy of the flashlight remained unchanged and was equal to 1200 W·s.

Fig. 15. Reaction times of semiconductor output (a) and relay output (b) of System A with the line sensor. Distance of the light source to a sensor (given after a colon): 5 cm (lamp shade without reflective material) and 70 cm (lamp shade with reflective material).

Fig. 16. Influence of the flashlight energy change on the recorded reaction time of (a) semiconductor output and (b) relay output of the System A with the line sensor along with a trend line, linear fit equation, and correlation coefficient R^2 .

D. Influence of flashlight energy change on the reaction times of system A with a line sensor

System A with a line sensor was subjected to measurements of reaction times with the changing flashlight energy, similar to the case of point sensors, keeping the distance of the flashlight from the line sensor at a constant value of 70 cm. System A with the line sensor did not detect flash if the flashlight energy was less than 600 W·s. The point sensor of the same System did not detect flash when the energy was less than 134 W·s. The results are shown in Fig. 16. Due to a narrower flashlight energy range than in the case of point sensors, a linear fit line was used instead of the power function used in Fig. 10 and 11.

E. Influence of the light source distance on the flash detection by a line sensor

Following the earlier measurement setup, it was verified if moving the flashlight away from the line sensor to 113 cm was

TABLE VI
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR SEMICONDUCTOR OUTPUT OF SYSTEM A WITH THE LINE SENSOR

System - output type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - semiconductor - 5 cm	2.400	2.304	2.452	0.148
System A - semiconductor - 70 cm	2.360	2.298	2.424	0.126
System A - semiconductor - 91 cm	2.414	2.374	2.466	0.092

going to have an influence on the reaction times of System A. It was found that this distance of the light source to the sensor was too large even when using the lamp shade with reflective material and the flashlight energy set to maximum. The maximum distance at which System A still detected the flash was 91 cm.

Fig. 17 shows the comparison of the reaction times of all three cases of the System A tests, including the line sensor.

TABLE VII
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR RELAY OUTPUT OF SYSTEM A WITH THE LINE SENSOR

System - output type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - relay - 5 cm	7.648	7.074	7.806	0.732
System A - relay - 70 cm	7.694	7.024	7.832	0.808
System A - relay - 91 cm	7.632	7.132	7.734	0.602

Fig. 17. Reaction times of semiconductor output (a) and relay output (b) of System A with the line sensor. Distance of the light source to a sensor (given after a colon): 5 cm (lamp shade without reflective material), 70 cm, and 91 cm (lamp shade with reflective material for both cases).

The results are also shown in Tables 6 and 7.

F. Results synthesis

Taking into account the tested configurations of IACDs described in this section, the main findings of the behavior of different systems are presented in Table VIII. This synthesis focuses on two main configuration options: type of output and type of sensor. The table summarizes the performance of the particular output, its suitability to trigger an internal arc fault

TABLE VIII
PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IACD CONFIGURATIONS

Feature / Consideration	Configuration	Implications
Output type	Semiconductor	Fastest operating; suitable as a control output to trigger internal arc reduction device (IARD); show higher dependency on the value of illuminance
	Relay	Characterized by contact bouncing and larger range of reaction times; less dependent on the value of illuminance; suitable as a secondary signal in a control system
Sensor type	Point sensor	Higher sensitivity to illuminance, which may result in nuisance tripping caused by switching arcs; easier to install and wire (sensors connected via shielded copper wire)
	Line sensor	Characterized by lower sensitivity to arc illuminance; can help in reducing nuisance tripping caused by switching arcs; long loops of such sensor need to be limited to a transportation unit

reduction device, and the behavior in changing illuminance values. In the case of sensor type comparison, the first aspect that is being compared is the sensitivity to the illuminance and the possible detection of switching arcs generated by normal operation of switching devices. This detection is classified as nuisance detection by IACD. The line sensor is advantageous in this case. However, it is more difficult to install it properly in comparison with point sensors due to the bending radii of loops of optical fiber and the need to limit the loops to a transport unit.

The I-MR charts used to detect special cause variation in the measurements taken are not intended to compare the process of manufacturing of IACDs, for which the I-MR or Xbar-R charts could also be used. This is the specific application of the I-MR control chart in this paper that focuses on displaying the measurement points, observing patterns, and points outside the control limits. Due to the number of measurement points, it was decided to use simple descriptive statistics displayed on a box plot and reproduced in the tables. Those include the median, maximum, and minimum values, as well as the range. Analyzing the results from Table IV, V, VI, and VII the IACD with a semiconductor output that reacts the fastest is System B with a point sensor. The IACD with a relay output that reacts the fastest is System C with a point sensor.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Based on the signals shown in Fig. 4(a), one can conclude that the semiconductor outputs are noticeably faster than the relay outputs and do not show contact bouncing, which has an influence on the speed of tripping of a main circuit breaker with an opening coil. The range of the reaction times of tested

IACDs is smaller for semiconductor outputs than for relay ones. Fig. 6 shows that the fastest reacting IACD is System B with semiconductor output. It reacted faster than System A with the same output type. On the other hand, point sensors of System B are more sensitive than those of System A. Point sensors of System B detected the flash in a broader range of flashlight regulated energy than those provided with System A (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11). Semiconductor outputs offer faster reaction times and narrower range of measured values, and therefore they are the preferred type of output used to limit the energy of an arc fault. Any additional delay to the reaction time of an IACD leads to more damage to the switchgear assemblies. For that reason, in the case of an IACD equipped with two types of output, semiconductor and relay outputs, the latter can be used as an additional indication of IACD operation in a control system.

From the IACDs tested, System C had only relay type outputs, characterized by the narrowest contact bouncing band (Fig. 4(b)) and the fastest reacting relay output (Fig. 4(a)). Most probably it is a result of the application of a better type of relays characterized by smaller contact bouncing and faster reaction times compared to the type of relays used in the two remaining systems tested.

Points outside the whisker of box plots, called outliers, visible in Fig. 6, 8, 9, 13, 15, and 17 can have two sources. For relay outputs they can be caused by the random nature of contact bouncing. In the case of semiconductor outputs that do not display that type of behavior, outliers are also observed. They can be linked to the way that IACD reaction times are distributed. The distribution of the reaction times does not need to be normal but can be a long-tailed distribution, which would result in outliers present in a box plot. In order to confirm this hypothesis, it would be necessary to perform a larger number of measurements on a few representative samples of each of the systems discussed in this article.

An important outcome of the analysis is the shortening of the reaction time of the semiconductor outputs when the illuminance increases as the flashlight is moved closer to the point sensors (Fig. 8). In the case of relay outputs, this influence is much smaller (Fig. 9). In practice a higher value of illuminance means higher energy arcs, that is, either an arc burning closer to a sensor or a higher current value three-phase arc as opposed to a one-phase arc between a line conductor and grounded part of metal enclosure of a switchgear assembly. What is noteworthy is that System B that is the fastest reacting IACD shows less dependence of operation speed on light source energy (Fig. 11). The reaction time of the semiconductor output of System A is more sensitive to the change in light source energy, which is represented by a power fit equation coefficient (Fig. 10). However, the point sensor of this system is the least sensitive out of all three systems tested.

Measurements conducted for a line sensor (only for System A) show a lower sensitivity to an external light source compared to that of the tested point sensors. This sensor reacted to a narrower range of energy of the flashlight. Therefore, the observed change in the reaction times of both semiconductor and relay outputs is smaller than in the case of the point sensor used with System A (Fig. 16).

Fig. 18. Comparison of the reaction times of System A with a line sensor and a point sensor: (a) semiconductor output; (b) relay output. Distance of the light source to the sensors is given after a colon.

The reaction times of System A with a point and line sensor can only be roughly compared because of the need to use a different lamp shade for these two types of sensors. If the same lamp shade, as for the point sensor, was used for a line sensor, the measurements would only be possible at a very short distance between the flashlight and the sensor. Nevertheless, a tabular comparison of the results (Table IX and X) and box plots (Fig. 18) were prepared comparing the reaction times of System A with a point and a line sensor.

Taking into account only a rough comparison of the two cases shown in Fig. 18, it is possible to observe that point sensors are more sensitive to flash and would result in faster operation than line sensors. The use of a particular sensor type needs to be preceded by an analysis of pros and cons for a given application. It must also be indicated that since the study was performed only for one system, the results cannot serve as a generalization of the observed behavior to the other IACDs available on the market. An additional study is required for other systems before similar conclusions can be drawn.

TABLE IX
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR SEMICONDUCTOR
OUTPUT OF SYSTEM A WITH THE LINE AND THE POINT SENSOR

System - output type - sensor type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - semiconductor - line - 70 cm	2.360	2.298	2.424	0.126
System A - semiconductor - point - 70 cm	1.636	1.618	1.684	0.066
Percent change	30.7%	29.6%	30.5%	47.6%

TABLE X
DIFFERENCES IN THE REACTION TIMES (MS) FOR RELAY OUTPUT OF
SYSTEM A WITH THE LINE AND THE POINT SENSOR

System - output type - sensor type - distance to the light source	Median	Min	Max	R (Max-Min)
System A - relay - line - 70 cm	7.694	7.024	7.832	0.808
System A - relay - point - 70 cm	6.872	6.480	7.022	0.542
Percent change	10.7%	7.7%	10.3%	32.9%

V. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This article presents a comparison of three commercially available IACDs. It is crucial to ensure the fastest possible detection of an internal arc fault and subsequent reaction of an IACD from the safety of personnel and the protection of a switchgear assembly point of view. The measured reaction times presented favor IACDs equipped with a high-speed semiconductor output. Thanks to this feature of an IACD it is possible to shorten the reaction time after the detection of an arc fault by a factor of a few milliseconds. The selection of an optical based IACD, the possibility of using different kinds of optical sensor (point or line), types of output (semiconductor or relay) are going to be essentially important for the speed of detection of an internal arc fault, and the limitation of its effects. It will also have an influence on how a system will react when switching arcs or external light sources during maintenance are present. The sensitivity to an external light source can be addressed by using an additional condition for the operation of an IACD based on the measurement of the current value or voltage distortion, characteristic for an internal arc fault.

An aspect that always needs to be considered is the cost of installing a system for arc detection [28], [29], even if it does not use a dedicated fast arc quenching device, but rather the main incoming circuit breaker as an arc reduction device (disconnection of power supply for a complete low-voltage switchgear assembly). From an initial cost point of view, it can be higher than the cost of an assembly providing passive protection against internal arc faults. Passive protection is obtained by strengthening the design of an assembly enclosure, so that it can withstand the effects of an internal arc, and by using internal compartmentalization and covers. However, taking into account the total cost related to damages caused by an internal arc fault, including the necessity to exchange a complete panel in a lineup and the related limitation of operation of an assembly when waiting for the delivery of

replacement parts, for some of the applications, it will be more advantageous to use an active arc protection. Active arc protection will be interesting for market segments where it is critical to ensure power availability and restoration of service of an assembly in shortest time possible. These could be related to powering manufacturing processes that, when disrupted by a power outage, cause material losses and have a negative impact on the environment. The cost of exchanging a panel or a large part of its equipment and the cost of downtime will compensate the initial cost of an internal arc fault mitigation system.

The sensitivity of a used optical sensor type to external light sources is of particular importance when it comes not only to the triggering of an IACD during maintenance but first of all when it comes to ensuring less sensitivity to detection of switching arcs caused by the normal operation of switching devices (contactors) or protection devices (circuit breakers). Based on the study limited to System A, line sensors provide less sensitivity to the detection of switching arcs. Similar conclusions are presented in [16] where the transmittance of different types of optical fiber is discussed. Less sensitivity to the detection of switching arcs can help in meeting the criteria to obtain the arcing class E defined in the new document IEC TS 61641 [21], which is under development. On the other hand, it must be considered that long loops of line sensors present challenges when a switchgear assemblies are transported to their installation site. For this reason, it is necessary to route a line sensor in a way that its loop is limited to a transport unit of an assembly. Comparison of the measured reaction times shows that a lower sensitivity of a line sensor may result in a longer reaction time of an IACD, which must also be carefully considered. This study has a limitation related to the fact that only one system with line sensors was tested, and it is not enough to generalize those findings to the other systems not subjected to measurements. The measurements were made with a flashlight used to trigger IACDs, and during test conditions with an internal arc fault in switchgear assemblies, the illuminance values are expected to be higher. As a result, the difference in the reaction time of IACDs equipped with line and point sensors can be smaller than that obtained through measurements presented in this article. However, it must be verified by an internal arc fault test. During preparation of the internal arc fault test, the reaction times obtained for different tested configurations will be used to install sensors in the test sample, taking into account their distance to arc ignition points defined in IEC TR 61641 [30] and the future IEC TS 61641 [21].

As a next step, measurements of the reaction times of a test setup consisting of an IACD and a circuit breaker are planned. The triggering of the IACD will also be done using the same flashlight, but measurement of reaction time will also include the time it takes to open a circuit breaker. This will allow us to select the fastest operating solution with an incoming circuit breaker acting as the Internal Arc Fault Reduction Device (IARD). Subsequently, the selected solution with different distances of the point and line sensors to the ignition points of the arc will be verified under internal arc fault conditions. This verification will provide data on the operation of IACDs

in real life conditions.

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